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1. Executive Summary

This report documents the GUTTA project progress in fulfilment of its specific and communication objectives during the reporting period ranging from 2021-07-01 to 2022-12-31, corresponding to RP6.

This is the second last period, and thus information in this report could be an input to make further minor corrections before project's end. Please note that full technical and financial information is declared on SIU platform and the present report just represents an overview of related contents.

It includes reference to project deliverables of this period as well as documentation of major unforeseen delays and achievements.

When not re-defined here, shortcuts refer to the public GUTTA Glossary, which can be found at www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3667198

2. Project progress

The report is organized into General achievements (Sect.2.1), unforeseen Issues (Sect.2.2), and a summary of project status by means of key metrics (Sect.2.3).

2.1 General achievements

During the 6 months of the present report, further management, communication, and technical progress was achieved by the GUTTA project.

Management

Besides ordinary day-to-day management, this period included the fourth Steering Committee meeting (held on Nov. 17, 2021). This was an occasion to recap on financial, technical, and communication advancements. Also, the preparation of the final events in both Croatia and Italy started.

Communication

Besides providing updates on project progress on various social media, in this period a high-level Interreg multi-project event was run together with the METRO and E-CHAIN projects (on Oct. 19, 2021). Furthermore, GUTTA activity was disseminated during two conferences:

the IMarEST annual conference (“Progress and pathways towards decarbonization” session) and a webinar by the IET (Institution of Engineering and Technology) on decarbonization of transport sector.

Technical

In the 6 months included in this report, crucial progress on SO1 was performed. In particular, the GUTTA-VISIR (GV) tool for least-CO₂ ferry routes in the Adriatic (<https://www.gutta-visir.eu/>) entered operations. In reference to SO2 feedback on GV and on recent legislative proposals (such as the “fitfor55” package) was collected. For SO3, work for understanding the COVID-19 dynamics from cross-border mobility data was carried out, in cooperation with MMPI’s subcontractor University of Rijeka.

2.2 Pending issues

During the current period, the main reason of concern regards AdSP. The organization joined the consortium late, due to internal administrative difficulties. Later, during the COVID lockdown and subsequent times, the collaboration slowed down and AdSP could provide only limited technical contributions to the project. However, AdSP announced hiring a new human resource for providing support to the implementation of GUTTA.

2.3 Status metrics

The status of the project is monitored through both financial and technical implementation data, as reported in the following two subsections.

2.3.1 Financial absorption

The financial absorption, inclusive of implementation gaps, both at WP and activity level, is summarized in Fig.1-5. The titles of the activities are provided in Tab.1.

The definitions of the relevant quantities are as follows:

- Done: cumulative absorption since project start, divided by planned cumulative absorption;
- Gap: difference between to-be-spent and actually-spent budget in given RP, divided by planned cumulative absorption. Negative values mean overspending;
- Remainder: complement to 1 of the sum of done and gap.

Furthermore, in this annual progress report, information relative to RP6 is included. It is defined as the time between 2021-07-01 and 2021-12-31. Information on the budget breakdown at the level of budget lines and other details can be found in D.1.4.5.

Figure 1 WP1 and WP2 implementation status at the end of RP6.

Figure 2 WP3 and WP4 implementation status at the end of RP6

Figure 3 WP5 implementation status at the end of RP6.

Table 1 Activities executed in RP6.

A. number	Activity title
1.2	Day-to-day project management, coordination and internal communication
1.3	Steering and monitoring of the project implementation
1.4	Financial management
2.2	External communication
2.3	Direct engagement of stakeholders
3.1	Input data collection
3.2	Initial data analysis and planning
4.2	MRV - data collection guidance
4.3	Preliminaries for new CB maritime routes
4.4	Eco-routes DSS
5.1	Validation and demonstration

The overall implementation rate is defined as the actual cumulative absorption compared to the planned absorption. At the end of RP6, this indicator read **71.8%**.

More information on the breakdown of the budget absorption can be found in the financial report of RP6, corresponding to deliverable D.1.4.5.

2.3.2 Technical implementation

The progress advancement is monitored through the status of the Deliverables of RP6 in Tab.2.

Table 2 Status of implementation of deliverables of RP6 completed.

	D. number	D. title	Month due	PP in charge
1	1.2.5	Progress report #5	36	CMCC
2	1.4.5	Financial report #5	36	CMCC

3	4.2.3	User satisfaction with the THETIS-MRV system	33	CSA
4	4.4.1	Operational prototype of the DSS for Eco-routes	36	MMPI

All RP6 deliverables are complete and were submitted to the SIU system.

3. Conclusions

The implementation of GUTTA project activities was monitored by the present report.

The overall financial absorption is about 72% of planned, to be contrasted to 86% of the extended project lifetime (36 out of 42 months) elapsed. This is due to underspending from especially one PP, which still needs to be recovered.

The largest part of the technical work was devoted to deliver with respect to the programme output indicator “4.101 - Improved multimodal transport services”, which is covered by GUTTA SO1. Important progress on SO2 and SO3 was also performed and is documented in deliverables submitted in this RP.